

Stakeholders' perceptions on the impact of political decisions during the COVID-19 pandemic on the health system, and psychosocial, epidemiological and economic outcomes in Vienna and Lower Austria - protocol of a vignette-based qualitative study

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1 Introduction

Despite implementing more frequent and restrictive containment measures than most comparable European countries during the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic, Austria has not fared better — indeed often worse — regarding pandemic mortality rates and societal costs (EcoAustria, 2021; Bilinski et al., 2022). Although a complex conglomeration of factors contributes to how a country weathers a severe public health crisis, Austria's suboptimal preparedness (e.g. the inability to link data from different resources and inefficient communication strategies) has undoubtedly contributed to the challenges it has faced during the pandemic. Exploring and understanding the conditions and factors associated with the successful and failed policies that shaped the pandemic in Austria is essential to guide investments and plan for better preparedness and more effective response to future epidemics and pandemics.

In any epidemic or pandemic situation, non-pharmacological measures such as mandatory face masks, lockdowns, school closings, mass gathering prohibitions, or testing play an important role in the absence of effective treatments (Haug et al., 2020). Implementing such policies during the COVID-19 pandemic slowed the disease's spread and prevented deaths but also caused substantial economic and societal damages (Chakraborty & Maity, 2020) and harmed other health areas, such as mental health (Dale et al., 2021). Nationally, however, such policies' stringency has differed substantially. Throughout 2021 and 2022, the City of Vienna, for example, repeatedly enacted stricter measures than other Austrian localities, regardless of the number of COVID-19 cases. The incremental benefits or risks of both strict and lenient policies to contain infectious diseases in Austria during the crisis remain largely unexamined because Austria has never evaluated the effectiveness of its measures and policies.

Evaluating responsive policies following an epidemic or pandemic has been a state-of-the-art international approach for decades. For example, the World Health Organization (WHO) launched a joint external evaluation process to assess national capacities in epidemic responses following the 2013–2016 Ebola epidemic in West Africa (Blair et al., 2017), and Switzerland commissioned an external evaluation of its policies to overcome the COVID-19 pandemic (BAG, 2022). Such evaluations can provide deep insights into the appropriateness and performance of epidemic or pandemic response interventions in national settings. COVID-19 has the potential to provide Austria with a unique opportunity to learn from the crisis, reflect on past decisions, and improve public health preparedness for future infectious disease emergencies. By doing so, Austria can increase its ability to prevent, detect, and rapidly respond to future epidemic and pandemic threats.

The project BETTER ("*Being equipped to tackle epidemics right*"), funded by the Vienna Science and Technology Fund (WWTF), aims to analyse the perspectives of experts and stakeholders to determine which policy and epidemiological decisions and what other factors (according to experts and stakeholders) have had the most significant impact on the health system, psychosocial, epidemiological and economic outcomes. Furthermore, the findings will be used to develop well-founded recommendations to improve epidemic and pandemic preparedness in a densely populated urban region such as Vienna and a more rural, less densely populated region such as Lower Austria. The research objectives of the BETTER project for this study are:

Which political and epidemiological decisions (or lack of decisions) do stakeholders perceive as having the most substantial impact on the health system, psychosocial, epidemiological, and economic outcomes?

- a. How can we generalise these findings for better preparedness for future pandemics?
- b. Would stakeholders propose a different hierarchy or timing of decisions, and if so, what are the potential implications?

This qualitative vignette study describes stakeholder perspectives on political and epidemiological decisions (or lack of decisions) and other factors impacting citizens' lives. Narrative epistemology emphasises that exploring personal experiences and viewpoints facilitates a deep understanding of different individuals' motivations and preferences, which is vital to the sustainable implementation of research findings. With this approach, we want to ensure the findings and recommendations from the BETTER project can be used in the future and increase Austria's epidemic and pandemic preparedness.

2 Methods

Qualitative methods are ideal for exploring the scientific community's perspectives and facilitating interactions. Likewise, qualitative research allows considering lay citizens' preferences, which is crucial for effective pandemic management, as a large body of literature showed that citizens' and patients' preferences differed substantially from those of professionals and experts (Bravo et al., 2015). In addition, qualitative methods, especially action research methodologies, are well suited for topics where controversial viewpoints exist. They can also be used to assess the potential for implementing research findings in different contexts and developing policy recommendations that are acceptable and applicable to people with diverse backgrounds.

Study design and participants

A qualitative vignette-based study will be conducted in Austria, particularly Vienna and Lower Austria, involving two major participant groups. One participant group will consist of experts in health care, communication, education, economy, welfare and mental health, and citizen representatives such as patient advocates and self-help organisations on the national and state level. The other participant group will involve citizens. Special consideration will be given to gender- and diversity-related aspects in selecting interview partners. Sample selection will follow the maximum variation sampling strategy (Patton, 2015) regarding gender, age, educational level, COVID-19 infection/vaccination, living situation and other sociodemographic characteristics. We anticipate conducting 20–25 interviews but will stop sampling once data saturation is achieved, defined as the absence of new concepts in at least three consecutive interviews (Saunders et al., 2018). Data saturation is a widely used principle in qualitative studies to determine the appropriate sample size and assess its sufficiency. It refers to the point in data collection where gathering more data no longer provides new insights to the research questions (Patton, 2015). In our study, we will start analysing data as soon as the first transcripts become available and continue the analysis alongside data collection to identify the saturation point (Guest et al., 2006; Mosor et al., 2021). To be included in the study, participants needed to live in Austria, preferably in Vienna or Lower Austria, during the COVID-19 pandemic and give their written and oral consent. People who cannot follow discussions in the German language cannot participate. Members of the research team will contact eligible individuals by telephone or e-mail. If they are interested in the study, they will be informed in detail about its aims and procedures.

Data collection

For this study, we developed two hypothetical scenarios in the form of research vignettes. The vignettes are structured into a factual description of the problem and a personally affecting theme, enabling the interviewees to put themselves in the fictitious situation as quickly as possible. Following the recommendations of qualitative research, care was taken to ensure that the vignettes were not too abstract, as this would make them less acceptable to interviewees (Jenkins et al., 2010).

The vignettes deal with invented situations in the future in which a new virus spreads rapidly among the population in Austria. The first vignette describes the beginning of an epidemic in Austria, focusing on epidemiology and the health care system. Little is known about the virus at the time of this vignette. In a

second vignette, a situation in the midst of a pandemic is described with a focus on economics. At this later point in the vignette, treatments are already available to treat the disease that is caused by the virus.

The interview is structured into these two vignettes, each followed by interview questions about the fictional scenarios. We developed a semi-structured interview guide with open-ended questions regarding decisions, populations, measures, and outcomes. We added a sheet containing measures and outcomes which can be used during the interview as a reminder or suggestion. The vignettes and the interview guide have been pilot-tested and amended to become more easily understandable. Two to three experienced qualitative researchers will conduct the interviews. We will record the interviews (audio recording) and transcribe verbatim with the interviewee's consent. The transcripts will be anonymised. Interviews will last between 45 and 60 minutes.

Data analysis

We will conduct a framework analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) relying on the WHO-INTEGRATE COVID-19 (WICID) framework to categorise the outcomes (Stratil et al., 2020). Several research team members experienced in qualitative research will conduct the analysis, aided by qualitative analysis software. The transcribed interviews will first be read through to gain an overview of the collected data and become aware of the content. The data will then be divided into meaning units (defined as specific units of text, some words or phrases with a common meaning). Subsequently, the concepts contained in the meaning units are identified. All concepts will be combined into higher-level categories in the last step. The results will be reviewed by another researcher with extensive experience in the field of qualitative research prior to this project. In case of disagreement, the results will be discussed together to obtain a common understanding of the meaning of the data and the depth of the concepts until consensus is achieved. To uncover potential additional topics, we will utilise Natural Language Processing techniques along with Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) (Gefen et al., 2017; Ruiz et al., 2019). LDA is a method in natural language processing that employs unsupervised generative probabilistic topic modelling to extract the meanings of predefined topics from text data. After analysis, all audio files will be deleted.

Descriptive statistics will be used to summarise the characteristics of participants. We will use R (<https://www.r-project.org/>) for all calculations. We will identify which health system, individual (according to subgroups such as age and gender) and population outcomes each stakeholder group identified as relevant.

Reporting of the data

Study results will be published in a peer-reviewed article.

Rigour and accuracy of the study

To ensure accuracy and rigour of the qualitative analysis, all interviews will be performed according to a pre-determined interview guide; 10% of the transcripts will be coded independently by two researchers. In addition, two citizen research partners will review the results. In case of disagreement, the results will be discussed until consensus is achieved to obtain a common understanding of the meaning of the data and the depth of the concepts.

Ethical considerations

The local ethics committees approved the study (EK Nr: 1433/2022). We will inform participants about the study's purpose and procedures, and they have to give their oral and written informed consent to be included. All participants will be treated in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the Helsinki Declaration and all applicable local regulations. All project work will comply with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). According to the participant's will, data previously recorded could be kept in the database for analysis or deleted. Before and during the data analysis, participants have access to their data on request and the right to correct it if incorrect data was recorded. No risks are to be expected from participating in the study, nor will they gain any benefit. The participants can withdraw from the study at any time.

Data security

The data that we collect from this research project will be kept confidential. All data will be secured against unauthorised access. Collected information about the participating person during the research study will be stored safely at the Medical University of Vienna. Professional confidentiality rules bind all study personnel. Data will be completely anonymised if shared with other researchers and research institutions. Likewise, publications of this evaluation study will not include any personal information which might lead to the identification of participants. Participants have the right to submit a complaint to the national data protection agency about handling their personal data at any time.

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